

Oxidation of Thiosemicarbazide, its Metal Complex and Hydrazones by *N*-Chlorobenzamide in Aquo-acetic Acid Medium—A Kinetic and Mechanistic Study

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The kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide (TSC), its zinc metal complex and hydrazones by *N*-chlorobenzamide (NCB) have been investigated in aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) medium in the presence of perchloric acid. The hydrazones studied are benzaldehyde, propionaldehyde, acetone and acetophenone thiosemicarbazones. The oxidations follow first order kinetics in [NCB], fractional order dependences in [substrate] and inverse fractional order in $[H^+]$. Addition of the reduced product of the oxidant and variation in ionic strength of the solution have no significant effect on the rates of oxidations. The rates increase with the increase in acetic acid composition of the solvent. The rate-limiting steps have been identified in all the cases and the rate coefficients of these steps and the related activation parameters have also been evaluated. Validity of the deduced rate laws has been checked by recalculating the rate constants as [substrate] and $[H^+]$ are varied.

The chemistry of thiosemicarbazide and its derivatives has evinced considerable interest due to their biological activity, synthetic and analytical applications¹. They are well known metal chelating agents and find applications in the characterisation of aldehydes, ketones and polysaccharides. Most of the chemical research with thiosemicarbazides has been concentrated on the structure and bonding of their metal complexes in the solid state. Recently some work on the mechanistic aspects of their reactions in solutions has been initiated by our research group², exploiting the tool of kinetic study. As a part of these efforts, the kinetics and mechanism of oxidations of thiosemicarbazide, its zinc-metal complex and four hydrazones by *N*-chlorobenzamide have been studied in aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) medium in the presence of perchloric acid.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of oxidations of thiosemicarbazide, its metal complex and hydrazones by *N*-chlorobenzamide has been investigated in aquo-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) medium in the presence of perchloric acid. The oxidations at constant $[H^+]$ with multi-fold excess of [substrate] (5–50 times), showed first order kinetics. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots were unaffected by the changes in $[NCB]_0$ ($0.5-5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3}), establishing first order kinetics in [NCB]. At constant $[NCB]_0$ and $[H^+]$, the rates increased with increase in [substrate] ($0.5-5.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3}) and log-log plots of k_{obs} vs [substrate] were linear with varying fractional order dependences in [substrate] (Table 1). The rates decreased with increase in $[H^+]$ at constant ionic strength with an inverse frac-

TABLE 1—KINETIC DATA AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE, ITS COMPLEX AND HYDRAZONES BY *N*-CHLOROBENZAMIDE (NCB) IN AQUO-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID AT 303 K

Orders observed in	TSC	Complex	BALTSC	PALTSC	ACTSC	APTSC
[NCB]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
[Substrate]	0.76	0.40	0.50	0.47	0.30	0.57
$[H^+]_{eff}$	-0.60	-0.40	-0.91	-0.74	-0.70	-0.67
Activation parameters for path 1 :						
E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	94.4	104.0	76.8	91.9	92.2	77.5
log A	14.9	16.1	11.6	14.3	13.9	12.0
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	88.36	99.5	70.8	89.3	89.4	75.2
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol^{-1})	+20.00	+47.7	-42.6	+20.37	+11.7	-22.4
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	82.3	85.0	83.7	83.2	85.8	82.1
Activation parameters for path 2 :						
E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	102.5	97.1	97.6	57.4	68.7	68.4
log A	13.0	12.1	12.4	5.6	7.6	7.5
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	100.7	92.2	91.5	50.1	66.1	66.3
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol^{-1})	-1.9	-29.8	-27.7	-161.9	-108.8	-109.4
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	101.2	101.3	99.9	99.0	99.0	99.4

tional order dependence in $[H^+]$. The $[H^+]$ at different $[HClO_4]$ and constant $[substrate]$ were computed by measuring the pH of the solutions. Addition of the reduced product of the oxidant, benzamide had no significant effect on the rates of reactions. The rates increased slightly with the increase in ionic strength of the medium, but increased with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium, effected by increasing the acetic acid composition of the solvent (values not shown). The rates were measured at different temperatures (293–308 K) by varying $[substrate]$ at each temperature and the activation parameters were computed from the Arrhenius and Eyring plots.

The observed kinetics (Table 1) for the oxidation of TSC, its metal complex and hydrazones may be explained by a two-pathway mechanism, one through $[substrate]$ dependent path and the other through $[substrate]$ independent path as shown in Scheme 1.

Path 1:

Path 2:

where S is substrate.

Scheme 1

The combined rate law (1) based on paths 1 and 2 (Scheme 1) has been deduced.

$$-\frac{d[NCB]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [NCB][H_2O]}{K_1 + [H^+]} + k_3 [NCB][S] \quad (1)$$

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [H_2O]}{K_1 + [H^+]} + k_3 [S] \quad (2)$$

The values of k_3 for TSC, its complex and hydrazones were calculated from the plots of k_{obs} vs $[substrate]$ (Fig. 1) ($10^3 k_3$ (mol dm⁻¹ s⁻¹) = TSC : 40.0, complex : 13.9, BALTSC : 23.3, PALTSC : 29.1, ACTSC : 9.9, APTSC : 43.4).

If $K_1 \ll [H^+]$, then equation (2) takes the form,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [H_2O]}{[H^+]} + k_3 [S] \quad (3)$$

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k}{[H^+]} + k_3 [S] \quad (4)$$

where, $k = K_1 k_2 [H_2O]$. The constants k and k_3 computed from the plots of k_{obs} vs $[S]$ and k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ were used to recalculate the rate constants from the rate law as the other was varied and vice versa. The recalculated values and the experimen-

tal constants are reasonably in good agreement (Table 2). Further, the constants k and k_3 were calculated at different temperatures by varying $[substrate]$ at each temperature. Two sets of activation parameters corresponding to these constants were evaluated from the plots of $\log(k \text{ or } k_3)$ vs $1/T$ or $\log(k_1/T)$ vs $1/T$ (Table 1).

The reactivity of the substrates towards the oxidant is in the order, APTSC > PALTSC > TSC > BALTSC > ACTSC > complex. A detailed mechanism of oxidation of TSC/hydrazones is shown in Scheme 2.

Applicability of Taft equation³ has been tested for both the pathways. In the case of hydrazones,

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) k_{obs} vs $[substrate]$ and (ii) k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$; $10^3 [NCB]_0 = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, $I = 0.30$ mol dm⁻³, temp. = 303 K; (i) $10^3 [H^+] = 7.0$ mol dm⁻³, (ii) $10^3 [substrate]$ (mol dm⁻³) = 2.0 (TSC, hydrazones), 1.0 (complex).

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF RECALCULATED VALUES AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE, ITS COMPLEX AND HYDRAZONES IN AQUO-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID AT 303 K

$10^3 [\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{H}^+]_{\text{eff}}$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$											
		TSC		Complex		BALTSC		PALTSC		ACTSC		APTSC	
		Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.
2.0	2.14	15.3	20.2	8.6	5.8	16.7	28.6	22.5	25.1	20.5	17.7	25.9	31.6
5.0	4.07	11.8	13.4	5.2	4.5	11.5	14.0	14.9	15.5	11.7	11.1	17.7	20.1
10.0	7.08	10.1	10.1	3.6	3.6	9.0	8.7	11.4	11.5	7.6	7.7	13.9	14.3
20.0	11.5	9.3	7.1	2.7	2.9	7.7	5.5	9.5	7.3	5.4	5.3	11.8	9.8
$\times 10^2 [\text{S}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)													
0.5		5.8	4.5	2.3	2.8	7.8	4.8	7.4	6.3	5.3	5.1	9.3	6.1
1.0		7.2	6.1	3.6	3.6	8.0	6.3	8.6	8.2	6.1	6.5	11.0	9.5
1.5		—	—	5.0	4.2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.0		10.1	10.1	6.3	4.9	8.5	8.7	11.2	11.5	7.7	7.7	14.3	14.3
3.0		12.9	14.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	17.6	18.1
4.0		—	—	—	—	9.5	13.1	16.1	16.5	10.0	9.6	20.9	22.4
5.0		18.5	22.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	12.5	10.5	—	—

the following relations were found to be valid with the exception of one of the hydrazones,

$$\log k_3 = 1.08\sigma^* - 1.98$$

$$\log k = -0.15\sigma^* - 3.25$$

$$\log k_3 = 1.12 E_s - 2.0$$

$$\log k = -0.24 E_s - 3.18$$

The positive and negative values for polar constant (σ^*) indicate that electron-donating groups on the carbon atom of C=N bond increase the rate of reaction in path 1 and decrease the rate in path 2. Similar trends were also observed in steric effect plots.

The constancy of the free energies of activation indicates that the similar mechanisms operate in all the cases. Fairly large values for the free energy of activation may signal bond-breaking in the formation of the transition state. The plots of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger for both sets of values (Table 1) were linear with isokinetic temperatures of 330 and 320 K respectively. These values are higher than the temperature range employed in the present investigations, indicating that the reactions are enthalpy-controlled.

The effects of solvent composition on the rates of ion-ion, ion-dipolar and dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule reactions in the liquid phase have been described elsewhere⁴⁻⁷. The present experimental observations, i.e. increase of rate with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (by increasing the methanol composition of the medium, 30–70%, v/v) is in agreement with Amis concept⁴ for ion-dipolar molecule interactions and the reaction pathways suggest to explain the kinetic results. The observed effect may also be explained by Laidler-Eyring equation⁷.

Experimental

N-Chlorobenzamide (NCB) was prepared by passing a continuous stream of dry chlorine gas into hot saturated solution of benzamide in 1 *N*

HCl⁸ recrystallised from alcohol (m.p. 116°). Its stock solution (0.10 mol dm⁻³) was prepared in double-distilled acetic acid. Thiosemicarbazide,

Fig. 2. (i) Plots of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger and (ii) plots of $\log k_{\text{eff}}$ vs % acetic acid; $10^3 [\text{NCB}]_0 = 10 [\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, $I = 0.30$ mol dm⁻³, $10^3 [\text{substrate}]$ (mol dm⁻³) = 2.0; temp. = 303 K.

TSC (Loba) was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. The complex, $\text{Zn}(\text{TSC})_2\text{SO}_4$ was

where R = PhCO

Scheme 2

obtained by mixing the concentrated solutions of TSC and zinc sulphate in 2:1 molar ratio. The complex was recrystallised from hot water and characterised by recording its ir spectrum. The hydrazones, benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (BALTSC), propionaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (PALTSC), acetone thiosemicarbazone (ACTSC) and acetophenone thiosemicarbazone (APTSC) were prepared⁹ by refluxing TSC and the respective aldehyde or ketone in equimolar quantities in alcohol for 2-3 h under acidic conditions. The hydrazones were recrystallised from alcohol (m.p., BALTSC:

160°, PALTSC : 143°, ACTSC : 177°, APTSC ; 113°. The stock solutions (0.05–0.10 mol dm⁻³) of TSC in water, the complex in 0.05 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ and the hydrazones in double-distilled acetic acid were prepared.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with [substrate] ≫ [oxidant] (5–50 times). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution, thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solutions containing known amounts of the substrate, perchloric acid, sodium nitrate, water and acetic acid (to maintain 1 : 1, v/v solvent composition), thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular time intervals. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within ± 4% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometries of TSC in the free and metal-bound states and hydrazones with *N*-chlorobenzamide were determined by allowing the reactions to go to completion at room temperature and different [HClO₄] (0.02–0.20 mol dm⁻³) and [substrate]/[oxidant] ratios. The products of the oxidations were identified by the standard tests¹⁰. Sulphate in the reaction products was estimated gravimetrically¹¹. The yields were 93 ± 4%. Nitrogen liberated was determined quantitatively by making use of a Schiff's nitrometer. A slow and steady current of pure and dry CO₂ was passed through the reaction vessel to sweep off N₂ to the nitrometer filled the 50% KOH, where CO₂ was completely absorbed. The volume of N₂ was noted and compared with the theoretical value. The observed stoichiometry per mole of TSC and hydrazones may be represented by equations (5) and (6),

where, R, R' = H, alkyl or aryl groups.

It was observed that CN⁻, aldehyde or ketone do not undergo further oxidations under the present kinetic conditions.

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